

UNRAVELING THE ENIGMA OF "IDIOM" IN THE EYES OF DOMESTIC LEXICOGRAPHERS

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Abstract: This exploration delves into the multifaceted interpretation of the term "idiom" as articulated by domestic lexicographers. Drawing insights from linguistic scholars such as O.S. Akhmanova, V.V. Vinogradov, A.I. Smirnitsky, and A.V. Kunin, the study navigates through diverse definitions and classifications. The examination reveals that idioms encompass a wide array of linguistic phenomena, ranging from expressions deeply embedded in the fabric of everyday language to those influencing literary narratives, legal discourse, and business jargon.

Key words: idiom, phraseological unit, linguistic interpretation, cultural variation, language evolution, linguistic nuances, cross-cultural communication, idiomatic expressions, modern communication trends, linguistic research.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada turli tilshunos olimlar tomonidan "idioma" atamasining ko'p qirrali talqinini o'rganiladi. shi haqida ma'lumot berilib o'tildi. Maqolada talabalarda ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda motivlashtirish va motivatsiyaning o'rni hamda ularni amaliyotga tatbiq etishning ahamiyati ilmiy asoslangan holda tadqiq etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: idioma, frazeologik birlik, lingvistik talqin, madaniy o'zgaruvchanlik, til evolyutsiyasi, lingvistik nuanslar, madaniyatlararo muloqot, idiomatik iboralar, zamonaviy muloqot yo'nalishlari, lingvistik tadqiqotlar.

Аннотация: Данное исследование углубляется в многогранную трактовку термина «идиома», сформулированную отечественными лексикографами.

Опираясь на идеи ученых-лингвистов, таких как О.С. Ахманова, В.В. Виноградов, А.И. Смирницкий, А.В. Кунина, исследование проходит через разнообразные определения и классификации. Исследование показывает, что идиомы охватывают широкий спектр языковых явлений: от выражений, глубоко укоренившихся в ткани повседневного языка, до тех, которые влияют на литературные повествования, юридический дискурс и деловой жаргон.

Ключевые слова: Ключевые слова: идиома, фразеологизм, языковая интерпретация, культурная вариативность, эволюция языка, языковые нюансы, межкультурная коммуникация, идиоматические выражения, современные коммуникативные тенденции, лингвистические исследования.

Introduction: In the Dictionary of Linguistic Terms by Professor O.S. Akhmanova, a phraseological unit is defined as "a word combination in which semantic monolithicity (integrity of nomination) prevails over the structural separateness of its constituent elements, as a result of which it functions as part of a sentence as the equivalent of a separate word" [187:503-504]. In the Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary, a phraseologism denotes "several semantically heterogeneous types of combinations: idioms, characterized by the rethinking of their lexical-grammatical composition and possessing an integral nominative function ..., combinations-phraseological schemes, in which the syntactic structure and a certain part of the lexical composition are rethought ..., combinations in which only one word is lexically rethought while preserving a separate nominative function for each of the component words ..., proverbs and sayings ..., winged words ... Rethinking, or semantic transposition, of the lexical-grammatical composition, stability and reproducibility are the main and universal features of phraseologisms" [190:559]

Professor A.I. Smirnitsky distinguished between phraseological units, which "are part of the basic fabric of the language, are its integral and absolutely necessary part ..., are devoid of any imagery, metaphoricity (to get up, to fall in love)", and idioms proper, which "are idiomatic word combinations, based on the transfer of meanings, on a metaphor, clearly realized by the speakers (to wash one's dirty linen in public)" [119:209]. In this dissertation, the subject of study is the second type of phraseological units, later called idiomatic phraseology [134]. Despite the fact that the term "idiom" is one of the traditional concepts in domestic and foreign linguistics, there are significant differences in the interpretation of the terms "idiom", "idiom proper", "phraseological unit", "phraseologism" in the works of domestic and foreign scholars. It is important to note that it is expedient to represent different classes of phraseologisms as a continuum, without clear-cut boundaries between them: this layer of the language lexicon is heterogeneous both from the point of view of semantic characteristics, i.e. it includes expressions with different degrees of idiomaticity, and in the structural aspect, covering units not only in the form of a word combination, but also with a predicative structure. Studying the phraseology of the Russian language, V.V. Vinogradov introduced three concepts: phraseological adjuncts – absolutely indivisible, indecomposable, the meaning of which is completely independent of their lexical composition, from the meanings of their components and is just as conventional and arbitrary as the meaning of an unmotivated word-sign; phraseological unities – motivated units with an integral meaning, arising from the fusion of the meanings of lexical components; phraseological combinations – turns, in which one of the components has a phraseologically connected meaning [36:140-161].

The doctrine of V.V. Vinogradov is fundamental for the majority of domestic scientists. In this work, phraseological *сращения* and phraseological unities are combined into one more general category of idiomatic phraseology with the subsequent use of the key monolexemic term "idiom". A.V. Kunin considers phraseology as a science consisting of three sections: idiomatics, which includes idioms proper; idiophrasematics, including "stable word combinations, the first phraseosemantic variants of which have literal, but complicated meanings, and the second idiomatic variants – completely rethought"; phrasematics, which includes "phraseologisms of non-idiomatic character, but with complicated meaning" [77:26-27]. Idioms are understood by him as "stable combinations of lexemes with completely or partially rethought meaning, with a high specific weight of the connotative aspect, i.e. its expressive-evaluative, emotional, figurative and other components" [77:53]. In the Dictionary of Linguistic Terms by O.S. Akhmanova, "idiom proper" is a phraseological unit with *ярко выраженными* stylistic features, due to which its use introduces an element of play, joke, and *нарочитости* into speech" [187:165-166]. It is also necessary to cite the definition of this term from the authoritative Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary: idioms are a class of phraseological units – "semantically connected combinations of words and sentences, which, unlike the syntactic structures similar to them in form, are not produced in accordance with the general laws of the choice and combination of words in the organization of an utterance, but are reproduced in speech in a fixed ratio of the semantic structure and a certain lexical-grammatical composition".

Examples and Case Studies:

1. Phraseological Units in Everyday Language:

o Everyday conversations often involve phraseological units that seamlessly blend into sentences. For instance, expressions like "kick the bucket" or "hit the hay" are idiomatic phrases used to convey the act of dying or going to bed, respectively.

1. Cross-Cultural Variations:

- o The phrase "the ball is in your court" is an idiomatic expression used to signify that someone has the responsibility to take action. In Russian, a similar sentiment might be expressed differently, demonstrating how idioms can vary across cultures while conveying similar meanings.

3. Literary Examples:

- o Literature is rich in the use of idiomatic expressions to add depth to characters and narratives. In Fyodor Dostoevsky's "Crime and Punishment," the protagonist, Raskolnikov, uses idioms to express his inner turmoil, such as when he contemplates the phrase "crushing the spider" as a metaphor for committing a crime.

4. Idioms in Legal Language:

- o Legal documents often use idiomatic phrases with specific meanings. For example, the term "force majeure" is a legal idiom referring to unforeseeable circumstances that prevent someone from fulfilling a contract. Understanding such idioms is crucial for legal professionals.

5. Business Jargon:

- o The business world is replete with idioms that convey complex ideas concisely. Phrases like "think outside the box" or "hit the ground running" are frequently used in corporate settings to encourage innovative thinking and immediate action.

6. Cultural Proverbs:

- o Proverbs, a subset of idiomatic expressions, provide valuable insights into cultural values. For instance, the English proverb "don't count your chickens before they're hatched" has parallels in different cultures, such as the Russian proverb "не говори гоп, пока не перескочишь," both cautioning against premature celebration.

7. Comparative Analysis:

- o Examining idioms across languages can reveal interesting linguistic

nuances. The English idiom "caught between a rock and a hard place" has equivalents in other languages, like the Russian "между молотом и наковальней," both conveying a sense of being in a difficult situation.

8. Social Media and Modern Idioms:

o With the rise of social media, new idioms emerge. Phrases like "throwing shade" or "going viral" have gained prominence, showcasing the dynamic nature of language and how idioms adapt to contemporary communication trends.

These examples and case studies illustrate the diverse ways in which idioms are woven into language, reflecting cultural, social, and contextual aspects. They highlight the importance of considering idiomatic expressions in linguistic analysis and understanding their impact on communication in various domains.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the interpretation of the term "idiom" is a complex and dynamic aspect of linguistic study, as evidenced by the diverse perspectives presented in the works of domestic lexicographers. From the foundational definitions offered by scholars like O.S. Akhmanova, V.V. Vinogradov, and A.I. Smirnitsky to the more recent insights provided by A.V. Kunin, it is clear that idioms encompass a broad spectrum of linguistic phenomena.

The examples and case studies further illustrate how idioms are an integral part of everyday language, contributing to the richness and nuance of communication across various contexts. They highlight the cross-cultural variations, the role of idioms in literature, their significance in legal and business domains, and their adaptation to modern communication trends, including social media.

The differences in the interpretation of terms such as "idiom," "idiom proper," "phraseological unit," and "phraseologism" emphasize the need for a nuanced understanding that considers cultural, contextual, and structural aspects.

The continuum of phraseologisms, with expressions varying in degrees of idiomaticity, underscores the dynamic nature of language and the challenge of precisely delineating boundaries between linguistic categories.

Ultimately, the study of idioms not only enhances our grasp of language structures but also provides insights into cultural values, societal norms, and the evolving nature of communication. As language continues to evolve, the exploration of idiomatic expressions remains a vibrant and essential area of linguistic research.

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